

Deliverable 1.1

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Specification of the emc2 model

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1. A meshed foreground network of main streets is the backbone of an uninterrupted system of pedestrian public space, enhanced by multimodality

Factor	Specification
1.1 Foreground Mesh of Main Streets	<p>Configurational properties of main streets: <i>What it is:</i> Foreground street network is the street network with high levels of configurational centrality through scales (Hillier 1996). <i>Why it is important:</i> The foreground network gives insight about the distribution and intensity of pedestrian flows (Berghauer Pont et al. 2019), which is in its turn linked to the intensity of use of the buildings bordering it (retail and service taking advantage of high levels of pedestrian flows).</p> <p>Spatial structure of the foreground network: <i>What it is:</i> The elements of the foreground network are directly connected among them, creating whenever possible a meshed structure whose sides range from 400 m (central areas) to 1000-1500 m (peripheries).</p> <p>Pedestrian accessibility to the surroundings: Through this pervasive meshing of the urban area, even in the peripheries, most inhabitants and jobs will be at less than 10 minutes walk from a main street.</p>
1.2 Uninterrupted Public Space System with pervasive pedestrian multimodality	<p>Uninterrupted public space is necessary within all urban space: all the main streets are walkable, as well as the ordinary and capillary streets feeding them. Multimodality (especially transit and cycling) must be seen as options to enhance pedestrian accessibility beyond the 15min and must not presuppose car use to access their networks. Transit options compatible with the main streets (streetcars, buses) will use them whenever possible.</p>

2. The network of main streets develops synergies with ecological and with far-range mobility corridors and keeps its structure over time

Factor	Specification
2.1 Green & Blue Ecological Network connected to main streets	Green and blue ecological networks are made of undeveloped land of ecological significance. In order to produce ecosystem services to the urban population and to keep their inner functioning they must keep some degree of connectivity. Synergies with the main streets are created when easy connections are made from pedestrians to access these ecological corridors. Crossings and overlays are also possible, but taking care of not disrupting neither the ecological functions nor the human usage of public space.
2.2 Mobility Corridors serving main centres	Mobility corridors are necessary to assure long-distance connections within a metropolitan area and beyond it, with further destinations. However, the network of motorways and railways serving the main centers of the metropolitan area should disrupt main streets as little as possible using overpasses and tunnels. By creating multimodal synapses with city streets (P&R, transit stops) in a pedestrian-friendly environment, mobility corridors can feed the pedestrian flows on main streets enhancing their movement economy.
2.3 Structure preserving development	All networks evolve over time : the network of main street, green and blue networks, mobility corridor networks and even the network of ordinary streets serving new urban developments. However, these developments have to be structure-preserving (see Mehaffy and Salingaros on resilient urban systems) from the point of view of the main streets : new main streets add to the old ones without making them lose their status. A specific contribution to the adaptive city.

3. Locally, the main street acts as an accessible, dense and diverse center for a neighbouring area

Factor	Specification
3.1 Main Street as an accessible Center for pedestrians and cyclists	<p>Main streets cannot act as center if they are not easily accessible. But this centrality through accessibility acts at different scales :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • beyond the 15m, as main street are part of the foreground network (Hillier 1996) • within the 15m, main street must be locally accessible through connections to ordinary streets and to other public spaces <p>A multi-scale assessment of street centrality is thus necessary to identify main streets requirements in the emc2 model. Bicycle lanes and transit service should reinforce pedestrian accessibility to main streets.</p>
3.2 Main street as a dense, active and diverse Center	<p>The main street is characterized by higher built-up density than its surroundings and has great diversity of activities and services. Higher density in suburban context also means providing missing middle (Parolek 2020) with mid-rise buildings.</p> <p>Public-receiving activities (retail, public and private services, etc.) are mainly located on the main street or on the squares served by it. Activities on and around the main street benefit from the movement economy (Hillier 1996) and form a dense web (Salingaros 2005, Mehaffy et al. 2020), with narrow spacing among them (several activities per 100 m).</p>
3.3 Suburban Main Street: Accessible by Car, Walked from Peripheral Parking	<p>Some degree of car access to main streets is needed in peripheral and suburban areas to sustain the local concentrations of activities on them. Car access begs the questions of reducing negative effect of car flows on main streets and finding parking options compatible with abundant and convivial pedestrian space.</p> <p>Car-drivers should become pedestrians well before arriving to their final destinations and experience the main streets by walking. An inverse gradient of parking supply is needed : extremely limited on-street parking on main streets and squares (for disabled users only), some small parking lots and on-street parking at close walking distance from main streets, a few larger ones further away, above all when needed for intermodal connection with mobility corridors (see specification 2.2).</p>

4. The main street is pedestrian friendly and enhances public life

Factor	Specification
4.1 Active building frontage on the main street	<p>Build-up frontage around the main streets channels pedestrian movement, bounds visually the perceived space and offer the opportunity to locate activities on the ground floor.</p> <p>Visual requirements: Buildings, whether adjoining or detached, align to form an urban frontage and create a street corridor effect (Alexander et al. 1977, Gehl 2010). Terminated vistas can be used to avoid the impression of unending peripheral axes (Mehaffy et al. 2020).</p> <p>Hyper-local functional requirements: Higher building density gives living and working opportunities on the main streets. Ground floors are for activities (Gehl 2010). Arcades can offer a protected pedestrian space (Alexander et al. 1977, Mehaffy et al. 2020).</p>
4.2 Main Street as a walkable environment	<p>Pedestrian space is preponderant, ground-level pedestrian crossings are frequent and cater for all kind of users, trees offer a canopy (Jacobs 1993). Compositional differences exist between 3 kinds of main streets :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- large urban boulevards, i.e. > 30-40 m, can be fully multimodal and have several lines of trees, but must avoid separating too much the two opposing sidewalks- urban avenues (20-30 m) must make some compromise in multimodality and presence of vegetation but are more easily crossed by pedestrians- unplanned main streets (normally <20 m and less regular) could consider pedestrianization or shared space and should avoid on-street parking <p>Shared space can be an option even on larger main streets instead of ample sidewalks (ex. Mariahilfer Straße in Vienna).</p>

(4 continued) ...pedestrian friendliness goes beyond pedestrian movement

Factor	Specification
4.3 Main street as a hub for social interaction with soft interfaces	The social and economic goal of main streets is not only to allow ease of pedestrian movement. They aim at transforming as much of this movement as possible in stay and socioeconomic interaction. For this reason, façades are always active on the main streets (Gehl 2010), urban furniture (both public and private) catalyze stay and interaction, pockets of activity are developed in recesses of the urban frontage (Alexander et al. 1977) where they are not disturbed by pedestrian movement. Layered spaces at building edges give depth to the public/private interfaces using setbacks for public activities (Gehl 2010, Mehaffy et al. 2020) to give extra space to stay and interaction. Eyes on the street are developed by building facing the street (Jacobs 1961) to enhance safety of public space usage.
4.4 Main street as a beacon for shared urban values	Main streets are the repository of the urbanity within each sector of the metropolitan area. By organising the most important functions, by hosting the most frequented public space, by being bordered by some of the most valuable buildings, they are invested by human meaning and become the anchors of community values for inhabitants and city users of a wider area. They show the physical permanence of the community over historical time (Griffiths 2015).

5. The inside of the mesh is well connected to the main streets and accommodates functions outside of the movement economy.

Factor	Specification
5.1 Meshed Network of Local Streets	<p>Ordinary streets are connected, above all for pedestrian movement. Local loops can be allowed for motorized modes to avoid through-traffic.</p> <p>Meshedness of ordinary streets can also support future development on new main streets, intensifying the density of the foreground network (this is what happens when a former suburban areas evolves towards a more central place within the metropolitan area).</p>
5.2 Capillary Pathways Interconnected for Pedestrians (and cyclists)	<p>Serve a few buildings or a subdivision. They are interconnected (offer shortcuts), open to public use, but not necessarily meshed.</p> <p>The most culturally-specific elements of the street network (Hillier, Habraken) balancing privacy and publicness in residential areas.</p>
5.3 Distributed Parks in the core of the mesh	<p>Neighbourhood parks do not need movement economy, are within a semi-pedestrian environment, contribute to green/blue networks</p>
5.4 Integration of Activity Areas into the urban fabric	<p>When the interior of the mesh contains an activity area, this should be considered as an ordinary city with interconnected ordinary streets allowing easy pedestrian access to the main streets. Large retailers part of urban frontage, parking in the back.</p> <p>Direct logistical connections to the far-range mobility corridors from within the mesh.</p>